

The Effect of Three Distinctive Endodontic Sealers on the Push-out Bond Strength of Fiber Posts: An in vitro Study

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Introduction

Fiber posts are recommended for retention of the permanent restoration during the reconstruction of endodontically treated teeth with non-sufficient coronal structure. Fiber posts have low rigidity, their elasticity is more compatible with dentin. On the other hand, they show promising stress distribution; therefore, they are advocated because they result in less root fracture. Resin types of cement are usually used for the bonding of posts to the root canal walls. Fiber posts have excellent bonding properties to resin cement and dentin. During the cementation of posts, the bond between the resin cement and the root dentin might be affected by the type of endodontic sealer used for root canal obturation and can ultimately affect the retention of the post. The aim of this in vitro study was to evaluate the effect of three distinctive sealers (AH-26, Dorifill, and calcium silicate-based) on the Push-out bond strength of fiber posts cemented with a dual cure self-adhesive resin cement. The null hypothesis was that the type of root canal sealer had no effect on the push-out bond strength of the fiber post.

Methods and Materials

The crowns of 64 single-rooted teeth were cut off from CEJ, and the root canals were prepared using NiTi rotary instruments (Goldent, China). Then the samples were randomly divided into 4 groups. In group 1 (the controls) gutta-percha was used without sealer. In groups 2, 3, and 4, the canals were filled with gutta-percha using AH-26 (DENTSPLY Maillefer, Germany), Dorifill or ZOE (DoriDent, Austria), and BC (calcium silicate-based) sealers (MK Life, Brazil), respectively, by cold lateral compaction technique. After preparation of post-space (9mm) using peeso reamer #3 (Mani, Japan), the fiber posts (Glassix, Nordin, Swiss) were cemented in the root canals using dual cure self-adhesive cement (Bifix SE, Voco, Germany). Then 1-mm-thick sections were prepared from the coronal thirds of all the root canals and subjected to a push-out test (Universal Testing Machine, Zwick, Germany). Data were analyzed using the one-way ANOVA and post hoc Tukey's tests.

Discussion

The success of fiber post-cementation depends on the proper bond to the root canal walls. Studies have shown that cementation of fiber posts with resin cement results in better retention, less microleakage, and more resistance to tooth fracture. The bond strength can be measured using different techniques, including conventional shear, micro-tensile, pull-out, and push-out tests. The push-out test which uses a shearing stress at the dentin-post-cement interfaces, simulates the clinical conditions. In the present study, the minimum bond strength was recorded in the eugenol-based sealer. The reason might be attributed to the remnants of eugenol on dentin; since eugenol has phenolic compounds, it increases the release of free radicals and interferes with the polymerization of resin cement. AH-26 (resin-based sealer) has no reversing effect on the adhesion of resin cement. It is reported that the high bond strength of resin-based sealers is due to the presence of epoxy resin in their composition, which is similar to the composition of the resin cement. Based on the results of the present study, the reason for the insignificant difference between the bond strength of BC sealer and AH-26 might be attributed to the resin structure of these two sealers and also to the fact that the reins in the structure of these sealers do not compromise the adhesion of fiber post to the root dentin.

Results

The maximum bond strength of fiber posts was observed in Samples filled with AH-26 sealer (Table 1). Although the difference between bond strength in samples filled with AH-26 sealer and samples filled with BC sealer was not significant ($P>0.05$). Therefore, it can be stated that the maximum bonding strength of fiber posts belongs to samples filled with AH-26 and BC sealers. The results showed that the lowermost bonding strength belongs to the samples filled with ZOE sealer ($p<0.05$), although there was not a significant difference between the samples filled with ZOE sealer and the control samples ($P>0.05$). Moreover, there was not a significant difference between the samples filled with BC sealer and control samples ($P>0.05$), but there was a significant difference between the samples filled with AH-26 sealer and the control group ($P<0.05$).

Conclusion

Based on the results of the present study, the type of endodontic sealer used for root canal obturation can affect the bond strength of the fiber post. The maximum bond strength of fiber posts was observed in Samples filled with AH-26 sealer and the lowermost bonding strength belongs to the samples filled with ZOE sealer.

Study Group	Bond Strength
Control Group	5.56
AH-26	15.38
ZOE	2.63
Calcium Silicate-Based (BC)	11.79

Table 1. The mean±SD of the push-out bond strength (Mpa) of study groups